

The Mediating Role of Organizational Identification in the Relationship between Spiritual Leadership and Organizational Success: A Study on Commercial Banks in Menoufia Governorate

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Abstract

The overall objective of the research is to identify the role of Organizational Identification (OI) as a mediating variable of the relationship between Spiritual Leadership (SL) and Organizational Success (OS) at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. The research community consists of all employees of the commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted a sampling method to collect data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the research hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results; the most important of which are: (1) there is a statistically significant relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, altruism, meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, productivity) and OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership). The multiple regression model showed that there is an impact of SL on OI; (2) there is a statistically significant relationship between SL and OS (organizational survival and organizational growth). The multi regression model showed that SL influence OS; (3) there is a statistically significant relationship between OI and OS, and (4) there is a direct impact of OI on the relationship between SL and OS. OI plays a partial role in the relationship between SL and OS. The study also indicated that there is a direct impact of SL on OS. In other words, OI mediates the relationship between SL and OS.

The study referred to a number of recommendations; the most important of which are: (1) managers should be interested in the future vision of their units and departments; (2) managers have the element of hope and belief in the vision of the bank; (3) the altruism of leaders in the bank; (4) the conviction of all employees of the bank that their jobs are important and meaningful both to them and to others, (5) deepening the membership of the bank with all its employees; (6) managers' interest in raising the level of organizational commitment; (7) increasing productivity and continuous improvement; (8) identifying the desired needs of employees in order to improve OI; (9) the necessity of learning investment in the promotion and development opportunities for OS; (10) designing and implementing a series of training programs that raise awareness among leaders in terms of the concept, importance and areas of OI, and its positive effects; (11) The need to pay attention to continuous meetings and the practice of social and recreational activities, and (12) inviting employees to participate in the various decision-making processes of the bank.

1. Introduction

There are new concepts in the contemporary administrative business environment, the most important of which is SL (Fry, 2003; Chen & Yang, 2012).

SL is highly popular in education, health care, psychology, as well as in management research. There has been an increase in the number of studies carried out, which shows the interest in SL (Kluas & Fernando, 2016).

A number of researchers in social research, in general, and administrative research, in particular, have been interested in SL (Giacalone and Jurkiewicz, 2003).

SL plays an important role both in improving the level of organizational commitment and on productivity in addition to their positive impact on the individual, the teams, the building of organizational values, and sense of community (Jerry, 2009; Chen et al., 2013).

SL belongs to the Transformational Leadership School, which focuses on behavior, messages about vision, ambition, emotional feelings, ideological and moral values, attention to individuals, and intellectual motivation of the leader and subordinates (Chen & Li, 2013).

SL plays an important role in creating a positive working environment, new working relationships, and motivating subordinates in a manner that contributes to the organization's goals efficiently and effectively (Polat, 2011).

Organizational Identification (OI) is a relatively recent concept that has emerged in administrative research in general (Liu, et al., 2011).

The researchers' efforts in the literature of organizational behavior have shown that OI achieves individual self-esteem and increases the level of belonging between the individual and the organization (Saks, 2006).

OI is one of the forms of social identification. All organizations seek to have a clear link and integration between their vision and mission and their employees in a manner that contributes to the achievement of their goals efficiently and effectively (Simon, 2000).

The success factors of the organization are its activities, which are the responsibility of all staff members of the Organization at all levels of management (Meibodi & Monavvarian, 2010).

The organization's success depends on how well it invests in mental ability to impart and learn new knowledge (Dzinkowski, 2000). The success of the organization is tied to its ability to formulate a strategy that is consistent with the mission and vision of the organization (David, 2009).

In light of the above, the current study seeks to identify the role of OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership) as a mediating variable of the relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, love of altruism, meaning /significance of work, commitment, and productivity) and OS (organizational survival, growth) at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

2. Spiritual Leadership

2.1. Spiritual Leadership Concept

SL is the use of the leader of his spiritual side as one of the motivational behaviors of his subordinates in a way that helps them discover the moral strength that binds them to others (Lean, 2012).

SL is one of the types of leadership that seeks to satisfy the needs and desires of the employees in the organization by providing psychological needs that help them to continue working in the organization and communicate with others, and belonging to the organization in a way that leads to efficiency in the performance of business (Chun et al., 2012).

SL is one of the methods that can be followed to improve organizational performance through leaders' attitudes that motivate employees to achieve the goals and vision of their organization (Chen & Yang, 2012).

SL is one of the forms of leadership that can be followed by leaders in an organization in a way that achieves its goals efficiently and effectively (Karadag, 2009).

SL is a set of human values that constitute the working environment of an organization, where its employees demonstrate their abilities and skills (Burkhart, 2008).

SL is a set of aspects relating to the personality of the individual, which serves as the primary engine of the physical body (Wilson, 2008).

SL is a set of positive emotions, such as gratitude, forgiveness, and hope that have proven to help individuals engage in behaviors that contribute to productivity and the development of relationships within the organization (Bono & Mc Cullough, 2006).

SL is a form of leadership, and it seeks to transform the workplace into a more comfortable and productive place, on the one hand, and to provide the needs of employers and employees, on the other (Thanakappan, 2005).

SL is a phenomenon that occurs in the organization when the leader is honest and modest in his actions and behavior in the organization in a way that reflects his respect for himself and others. It is one of the forms of leadership that can be used to provide the basic needs of employees, on the one hand, and to achieve satisfaction, on the other in addition to changing the business philosophy towards the organization from being mutually beneficial with the organization that they are working to achieve their own values (Reave, 2005).

SL is a set of values, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to motivate one's self, on the one hand, and to motivate others, on the other. It is a reliable leadership technique in motivating subordinates to achieve high levels of organizational and productive commitment. It is a set of values, attitudes, and behaviors that stimulate one's self and others to have a sense of survival in spiritual life (Fry et al., 2005).

SL is one of the methods of integrating the values, processes, and systems of the organization with the values and aspirations of its personnel, i.e., creating an atmosphere of harmony between individuals and the organization (Benefiel, 2005).

SL aims to teach subordinates the methods that enable them to govern themselves and create the right conditions, so subordinates can work freely with their leaders within the organization (Fairholm, 1996).

2.2. Spiritual Leadership Dimensions

There are six dimensions of SL (Zavvareh et al., 2013; Polat, 2011). These can be explained as follows:

1. Vision

There must be a clear vision of what the organization would like to be in the future. The term vision was rarely used in leadership literature until the 1980s. At the moment, leaders in business organizations have had to give greater attention to future direction due to the intensity of competition and technological development. Spiritual leaders try to motivate subordinates through a clear vision of the organization.

2. Hope / Faith

Hope is the desire to expect achievement; faith is beyond hope or expectation of something desirable; faith is more than just a wish for something. It depends on values, attitudes, and behaviors that ensure certainty and absolute certainty that what is desired and expected will be achieved. In general, hope and faith are the sources of belief and conviction that the vision and mission of the organization will be realized.

3. Altruistic Love

Altruistic love is the sense of integration, harmony, and well-being resulting from the care, attention, and appreciation of both self and others. This concept; also, includes the values of patience, compassion, tolerance, humility, altruism, trust, loyalty, and sincerity. Altruistic love helps to get rid of destructive feelings, such as fear, anger, the feeling of failure, and others.

4. The meaning/significance of work

The concept of meaning refers to whether members of the organization believe that the functions they perform are significant and meaningful, and by engaging in work, individuals derive meaning and purpose from life. Individuals who have an internal motivation and drive to learn to find jobs. Also, individuals who want to be members of the workgroup feel they have value and contribution to performance. It is clear that meaning and sense of importance are associated with spirituality in the workplace.

5. Membership

Most individuals tend to work in a group or team, and they prefer to work in an environment in which leaders appreciate their contributions to achieving their goals. Leaders must, therefore, be able to create a culture that involves leaders and subordinates interested and responsible for themselves and others. This culture must create a sense of membership. SL must, therefore, take care of the employees in such a way as to create an atmosphere of friendliness and trust among all staff of the organization.

6. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is one of the main axes of organizational success. SL plays an important role in influencing the level of organizational commitment. The appropriate leadership styles lead to an increased level of job satisfaction for employees. SL also plays an important role in achieving organizational identification and organizational loyalty through organizational commitment and the desire to remain and work in the organization.

7. Productivity

The availability of the element of hope / faith in the vision of the organization, their sense of importance and membership makes them do their best to carry out activities that achieve the vision of the Organization and thereby increase productivity. It should be noted that SL plays an important role in increasing the level of job satisfaction, which in turn leads to increased productivity in the organization.

3. Organizational Identification

3.1. Organizational Identification Concept

OI is the existence of some kind of correlation between the worker and the organization in which he or she operates. This can be illustrated by the need to align the objectives of the organization with those of its employees and the need for the individual to promote and develop the organization in which he or she works, whether at work or outside (Karanika-Murra, 2015).

OI is the degree to which an individual knows for himself in the organization the same characteristics and attributes that the organization is thought to be described (Milton & Westphal, 2005).

OI is the individual's adoption of the values and objectives of the organization as its own values and goals. In other words, OI is the process of integrating the desires of personal employees with the wishes of the organization in which they work (Johnson et al., 1999).

OI is a type of interdependence and positive psychological compatibility between the individual and the organization in which he operates (Stuart, 1999).

OI is the unification of the values and goals of the individual with the organization at which he works, his sense of integration, loyalty and commitment to it, and the desire to belong and membership (Street, 1994).

OI is the degree to which the characteristics of an individual are similar to those of the organization in which they operate (Dutton et al., 1994).

OI is the unity and conformity of the individual with the organization in which he operates, and his sense of allegiance and belonging to it (Mael & Ashforth, 1992).

OI is that individuals' working in the organization reshaping their concepts to conform to the concepts of the organization at which they work (Tompkins & Cheney, 1985).

OI is the process of integrating and matching the goals and characteristics of the individual to the goals and characteristics of the organization in which he operates (Hall et al., 1970). It is an individual's perception and conformity with the organization to which he belongs. OI includes three dimensions: loyalty, similarity, and membership (Cheney, 1982).

3.2. Organizational Identification Dimensions

The dimensions of OI are organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership (Cheney, 1982). These can be illustrated as follows:

1. Organizational Loyalty

Organizational loyalty is the loyalty of the individual to the organization at which he works and the enthusiasm towards achieving its goals and defending it in front of others.

2. Organizational Similarity

The organizational similarity is the individual's perception of the existence of a set of characteristics, values, and goals shared with the members of the organization in which he operates.

3. Membership

Membership is the concept of the individual itself in terms of the extent of its association with the organization, and the sense of belonging and the psychological connection between him and the organization and its members.

4. Organizational Success

4.1. Organizational Success Concept

OS is the success of the project as a balancing of competition requirements related to quality, time, cost, and meeting different desires and expectations (Aga et al., 2016).

OS is the achievement of the organization's goals in terms of different aspects of performance in terms of financial perspective, customers, internal processes, learning, and organizational growth. (Donsophon et al., 2016).

OS is the degree to which the organization is able to achieve its long-term sustainability objectives (Fleck, 2009).

OS is the ability of the organization to achieve its mission and objectives in order to achieve outstanding performance. The key elements of OS can be expressed in the form of an equation that is OS = message + strategic objectives + outstanding performance (Whitney, 2010).

OS is the organization's ability to coordinate its activities in the light of a shared vision of all stakeholders with the aim of achieving its objectives (Dell & Kramer, 2003).

OS is the ability of the organization to achieve its long-term goals and to achieve a balance between its goals and those of its employees (Kenny, 2001).

OS is the ability of the organization to achieve the organization's goals through expansion, renewal, organizational survival, and continued delivery of products or services to markets (Whetten, 1987).

4.2. Organizational Success Dimensions

The OS dimensions of the organization are organizational survival and organizational growth (Simon et al., 2011). These can be illustrated as follows:

1. Organizational survival

It means the organization's ability to achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty. There should be a system for receiving customer complaints and suggestions. Satisfaction should be a part of the culture of the organization and all employees involved in decision making.

2. Organizational growth

It means the ability of the organization to fulfill its social responsibilities, to ensure the training of employees, to be keen on identifying the needs and desires of the parties working with the organization, and the need to conduct studies and meetings to identify the satisfaction of employees and the need for diversity in incentive programs and; finally, the need to pay attention to the language of dialogue with the staff of the organization.

3. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of SL. There is one dependent variable of OS. There is one mediating variable of OI. It shows the rational link among the three types of observed variables. From the above discussion, the research model is as shown in Figure below.

Figure (1)
Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that OI plays a significant role in the relationship between SL and OS. SL as measured consisted of vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity (Fry & Matherly, 2006). OI is measured in terms of organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership (Cheney, 1982). OS is measured in terms of organizational survival and organizational growth (Simon et al., 2011).

4. Research Questions

The researcher has reached the research problem through two sources. The first source is available in the previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the

analysis of the relationship between SL, OI, and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

In light of the review of previous studies towards SL, literature has shown that there is a significant relationship between SL and organizational commitment, productivity, and satisfaction (Fry et al., 2017). SL positively influences the spirituality of the work environment (Afsar et al., 2016). There is a statistically significant relationship between SL and OCB (Kaya, 2015). There is a significant relationship between SL and organizational learning (Shafiqhi et al., 2013). There is a relationship between SL and job satisfaction (Masouleh et al., 2013). In addition, SL leads to increased behavior of OCB (Chen & Yang, 2012).

As for OI, the literature suggests that social responsibility and OI mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment (Erkutlu et al., 2016). While another study showed that OI significantly affects the relationship between mental integrity and organizational creativity (Liu et al., 2016), one of the studies has shown that customer orientation is a mediating variable in linking OI and job performance (He et al., 2015). Another study indicated that there is a significant relationship between leadership and OI (Ceri-Booms, 2010).

Finally, the literature review for OS has shown that effective governance enhances OS (Musawir et al., 2017). However, another study has shown that organizational learning plays a key role in achieving OS (Saadat et al., 2016). One of the studies has revealed a significant relationship between the maturity of project management and OS (Berssaneti & Carvalho, 2015). Another study indicated that there is a statistically significant relationship between strategic capacities and OS (Simon et al., 2011).

The second source for the research problem is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship between SL, OI and OS. The researcher found, through the pilot study, several indicators; notably the important and vital role that could be played by SL in reinforcing OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions of this study are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity), and OI at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate?
- Q2: What is the extent of the relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity) and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate?
- Q3: What is the nature of the relationship between OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership) and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate?
- Q4: What is the role of OI as a mediating variable of the relationship between SL and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate?

5. Research Hypotheses

In the light of a review of previous studies towards SL, literature has shown that SL plays an important role in influencing the spirituality of the work environment (Sani et al., 2016). There is a relationship between SL and organizational performance. SL has a positive impact on organizational performance (Salehzadeh et al., 2015). There is a significant correlation between SL and the quality of the career (Bardmili et al., 2013). There is a positive correlation between SL and the happiness of working individuals (Zavareh et al., 2013). There is a relationship between SL and employee empowerment (Esfahani et al., 2013). There is a positive relationship between SL and organizational outcomes, such as organizational commitment and productivity (Fry et al., 2017). There is a relationship between SL and organizational culture. Attendance as one of the dimensions of SL plays an important role in influencing performance, which has an impact on organizational culture (Karadag, 2009).

As for OI, literature has shown that organizational justice plays an important role in influencing OI (Terzi et al., 2017). There is a positive correlation between OI and OCB (Callea et al., 2016). However, another study showed an indirect relationship between OI and job satisfaction (Karanika et al., 2015). One of the studies has shown that there is a statistically significant relationship between OCB and OI (Demir, 2015). In addition, there is a relationship between servant leadership and both OI and OCB. Another study found that there is a relationship between OI and OCB. A third study has shown that OI mediates the relationship between servant leadership and OCB (Vondey, 2010).

Finally, the literature review for OS has shown that there is a positive relationship between management strategy and OS. Both job satisfaction and OCB play the mediating role between management strategy and OS (Donsophon et al., 2016). However, another study showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between funding leadership and OS (Aga et al., 2016).

The following hypotheses were developed to test if there is a significant correlation between SL, OI and OS.

H1: SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity) has no statistically significant effect on OI at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

H2: There is no statistically significant relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity) and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

H3: There is no statistically significant impact of OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership) of employees and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

H4: There is no statistically significant effect of OI as a mediating variable between SL and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

6. Research Strategy

6.1. Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. This sector includes three banks: National Bank of Egypt, Banque Misr, and Banque Du Caire. This explains why the population of this study includes 734 employees. The random sampling was used for collecting the primary data as it was difficult to get all of the items of the research population because of time limitations. The stratified random sample was used while selecting items from the different categories of employees. The following equation determines the sampling size (Daniel, 1999):

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

Accordingly, the sample size has become 322 employees at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size on the Population

Job Category	Number	Percentage	Size of Sample
National Bank of Egypt	245	34%	322 X 34% = 109
Banque Misr	317	43%	322 X 43% = 138
Banque Du Caire	172	23%	322 X 23% = 75
Total	734	100%	322 X 100% = 322

Source: Personnel Department at Commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate, 2017

Proportionality with the number of employees in the research population is proved in Table (1). By using the lists of employees at the Staff Affairs Department, commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate random choice of categories was attained. Table (2) illustrates the features of sample units.

Table (2) Frequency Distribution Table of Demographics

	Variables	Number	Percentage
1- Job Title	General Manager	15	%5
	Deputy General Manager	20	%7
	Agent General Manager	20	%7
	Deputy Manager	30	%10
	Controller	30	%10
	Excellent Banker	45	%15
	Banker A	40	%13
	Banker B	100	%33
	Total	300	100%
2- Marital Status	Married	200	%67
	Single	100	%33
	Total	300	100%
3- Age	Less than 30 years	120	%40
	From 30 to 45	130	%44
	More than 45	50	%16
	Total	300	100%
4- Educational Level	University Education	160	%54
	Post Graduate Studies	140	%46
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	50	%16
	From 5 to 10	150	%50
	More than 10	100	%34
	Total	300	100%

6.2. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the significant role of OI in the relationship between SL and OS. A survey research method was used to collect data in this study. The questionnaire included four questions, relating to SL, OI, OS, and biographical information of employees at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. Data collection took approximately two months. About 322 survey questionnaires were distributed by employing diverse modes of communication, such as in person and by post. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 93%.

6.3. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 35-item scale SL section is based on Fry & Matherly, 2006. There were five items measuring vision, five items measuring hope/faith, seven items measuring altruistic love, four items measuring the meaning/significance of work, five items measuring membership, four items measuring commitment, and five items measuring productivity.

The 23-item scale OI section is based on Cheney, 1982. There were seven items measuring organizational loyalty, seven items measuring organizational similarity and nine items measuring membership. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure OI at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

The 10- item scale of OS section is based on Simon et al., 2011. There were four items measuring organizational survival, and six items measuring organizational growth.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

6.4. Methods of Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach’s Alpha, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (3) the statistical testing of hypotheses which includes F- test and T-test. They are found in SPSS.

Also, the researcher used the Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) to measure the direct and indirect effects of SL on OS, as well as the measurement of the intermediate role of OI, through the indicators of conformity of alternative models on the one hand, and the model that achieves these indicators on the other.

7. Hypotheses Testing

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out means and standard deviations of SL, OI, and OS.

Table (3) shows the mean and standard deviations of SL, OI and OS

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
SL	Vision	4.146	0.769
	Hope/Faith	4.122	0.810
	Altruistic Love	3.709	0.814
	Meaning/Calling	3.887	0.832
	Membership	4.059	0.736
	Organizational Commitment	4.080	0.799
	Productivity	3.850	0.867
	Total Measurement	3.967	0.688
OI	Organizational Loyalty	3.681	0.809
	Organizational Similarity	3.613	0.871
	Membership	3.612	0.938
	Total Measurement	3.634	0.869
OS	Organizational survival	3.793	1.06
	Organizational growth	3.556	0.887
	Total Measurement	3.651	0.911

According to Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity). According to Table (4), among the various facets of SL, most of the respondents identified the presence of vision ($M=4.146$, $SD=0.769$), hope/faith ($M=4.122$, $SD=0.810$), altruistic love ($M=3.709$, $SD=0.814$), meaning/significance of work ($M=3.887$, $SD=0.832$), membership ($M=4.059$, $SD=0.736$), organizational commitment ($M=4.080$, $SD=0.799$), and productivity ($M=3.850$, $SD=0.867$),

The second issue examined was the different facets of OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership). Most of the respondents identified the presence of organizational loyalty ($M=3.681$, $SD=0.809$), organizational similarity ($M=3.613$, $SD=0.871$), and membership ($M=3.612$, $SD=0.938$).

The third issue examined was the different facets of OS (organizational survival and organizational growth). According to Table (4), among the various facets of OS, most of the respondents identified the presence of organizational survival ($M=3.793$, $SD=1.06$), and organizational growth ($M=3.556$, $SD=0.887$).

7.1. Evaluating Reliability

Data analysis was conducted. All scales were first subjected to reliability analysis. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to assess the reliability of the scales. Item analysis indicated that dropping any item from the scales would not significantly raise the alphas.

Table (4) Reliability of SL, OI and OS

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
SL	Vision	5	0.834
	Hope/Faith	5	0.820
	Altruistic Love	7	0.808
	Meaning/Calling	4	0.817
	Membership	5	0.808
	Organizational Commitment	4	0.837
	Productivity	5	0.915
	Total Measurement	35	0.960
OI	Organizational Loyalty	7	0.898
	Organizational Similarity	7	0.925
	Membership	9	0.968
	Total Measurement	23	0.980
OS	Organizational survival	4	0.961
	Organizational growth	6	0.875
	Total Measurement	10	0.941

To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach’s Alpha test was conducted. Table (4) shows the reliability results for SL, OI and OS. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were therefore excellent, according to Landridge’s (2004) criteria.

Table (4) presents the reliability of SL. The reliabilities of s vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity are generally higher. The 35 items of SL are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.960. The vision, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.834. The 5 items related to hope/faith are reliable

because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.820, while the 7 items of altruistic love are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.808. The meaning/significance of work which consists of 4 items is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.817. The 5 items related to membership are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.808, while the 4 items of organizational commitment are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.837. Productivity which consists of 5 items is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.915. Thus, the internal consistency of SL can be acceptable. According to Table (4), the 23 items of OI are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.980. The organizational loyalty, which consists of 7 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.898. The 7 items related to organizational similarity are reliable because Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.925, while the last nine-item (membership) is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.968. Thus, the reliability of OI can be acceptable.

Table (4) presents the reliability of OS. The 10 items of OS are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.941. The organizational survival, which consists of 4 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.961. Furthermore, organizational growth that consists of 6 items is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.875. Thus, the reliability of OS can be acceptable. Accordingly, three scales were defined, SL (35 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented about 0.960, OI (23 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented about 0.980, and OS (10 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented 0.941.

7.2. The Correlation among the Research Variables

Table (5) Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	SL	OI	OS
Spiritual Leadership	3.967	0.688	1.000		
Organizational Identification	3.634	0.869	0.692**	1.000	
Organizational Success	3.651	0.911	0.682**	0.855**	1.000

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Table (5) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of significant correlation between variables (SL, OI and OS). The level of SL is high (Mean=3.967; SD=0.688), while OI is high (Mean=3.634; SD=0.869), which led to higher OS (Mean=3.651; SD=0.911).

Table (5) reveals the correlation between SL and OI (R=0.692; P <0.01), which means that the high level of SL leads to higher OI. The table shows the correlation between OI and OS (R= 0.855; P < 0.01), and this shows that the high level of OI contributes to mitigation of feelings of OS. Finally, Table (5) refers to the correlation between SL and OS (R= 0.682; P < 0.01) implying that the high level of SL increases OS.

7.3. Spiritual Leadership and Organizational Identification

The relationship between SL and OI is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity) and OI at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

Table (6) Correlation between SL and OI

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Vision	1							
Hope/Faith	0.853**	1						
Altruistic Love	0.680**	0.716**	1					
Meaning/Calling	0.734**	0.456**	0.583**	1				
Membership	0.887**	0.837**	0.642**	0.765**	1			
Commitment	0.862**	0.971**	0.755**	0.471**	0.817**	1		
Productivity	0.654**	0.370**	0.521**	0.959**	0.717**	0.380**	1	
OI	0.669**	0.682**	0.564**	0.478**	0.664**	0.667**	0.453**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Based on the Table (6), the correlation between SL (vision) and OI is 0.669. For SL (hope/faith) and OI, the value is 0.682, whereas SL (altruistic love) and OI show a correlation value of 0.564. Also, the

correlation between SL (meaning/calling) and OI is 0.478. For SL (membership) and OI, the value is 0.664 whereas SL (organizational commitment), and OI shows a correlation value of 0.667. Finally, the correlation between SL (productivity) and OI is 0.453. The overall correlation between SL and OI is 0.692.

Table (7) MRA Results for SL and OI

The Variables of SL	Beta	R	R ²
1. Vision	0.197	0.669	0.447
2. Hope/Faith	0.522**	0.682	0.465
3. Altruistic Love	0.100	0.564	0.318
4. Meaning/Calling	0.367*	0.478	0.228
5. Membership	0.055	0.664	0.440
6. Organizational Commitment	0.125	0.667	0.444
7. Productivity	0.438**	0.453	0.205
▪ MCC		0.722	
▪ DC		0.521	
▪ Calculated F		45.444	
▪ Degree of Freedom		7, 292	
▪ Indexed F		2.63	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	

** P < .01 * P < .05

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

As Table (7) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.722 demonstrates that the independent variables of SL construe OI significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, independent variables of SL can explain 52% of the total factors in OI level. Hence, 48% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

7.4. Spiritual Leadership and Organizational Success

The relationship between SL and OI is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: There is no relationship between SL (vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity) and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

Table (8) Correlation between SL and OS

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Vision	1							
Hope/Faith	0.853**	1						
Altruistic Love	0.680**	0.716**	1					
Meaning/Calling	0.734**	0.456**	0.583**	1				
Membership	0.887**	0.837**	0.642**	0.765**	1			
Commitment	0.862**	0.971**	0.755**	0.471**	0.817**	1		
Productivity	0.654**	0.370**	0.521**	0.959**	0.717**	0.380**	1	
OS	0.635**	0.636**	0.522**	0.523**	0.667**	0.648**	0.498**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Based on the Table (8), the correlation between SL (vision) and OS is 0.635. For SL (hope/faith) and OS, the value is 0.636, whereas SL (altruistic love) and OS show a correlation value of 0.522. Also, the correlation between SL (meaning/calling) and OI is 0.523. For SL (membership) and OS, the value is 0.667 whereas SL (organizational commitment), and OS shows a correlation value of 0.648. Finally, the correlation between SL (productivity) and OS is 0.498. The overall correlation between SL and OS is 0.682.

Table (9) MRA Results for SL and OS

The Variables of SL	Beta	R	R ²
1. Vision	0.219*	0.669	0.447
2. Hope/Faith	0.086	0.682	0.465
3. Altruistic Love	0.113	0.564	0.318
4. Meaning/Calling	0.060	0.478	0.228
5. Membership	0.070	0.664	0.440
6. Organizational Commitment	0.646**	0.667	0.444
7. Productivity	0.430**	0.453	0.205
▪ MCC		0.711	
▪ DC		0.506	
▪ Calculated F		42.659	
▪ Degree of Freedom		7, 292	
▪ Indexed F		2.63	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.711 demonstrates that the independent variables of SL construe OS significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, independent variables of SL can explain 51% of the total factors in OS level. Hence, 49% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

7.5. Organizational Identification and Organizational Success

The relationship between OI and OS is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership) and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

Table (10) Correlation between OI and OS

Variables	1	2	3	4
Organizational Loyalty	1			
Organizational Similarity	0.949**	1		
Membership	0.968**	0.978**	1	
OS	0.842**	0.866**	0.834**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Based on the Table (10), the correlation between OI (organizational loyalty) and OS is 0.842. For OI (organizational similarity) and OS, the value is 0.866, whereas OI (membership) and OS show a correlation value of 0.834. The overall correlation between OI and OS is 0.855.

Table (11) MRA Results for OI and OS

The Variables of OI	Beta	R	R ²
1. Organizational Loyalty	0.501**	0.842	0.708
2. Organizational Similarity	1.11**	0.866	0.749
3. Membership	0.738**	0.834	0.695
▪ MCC		0.877	
▪ DC		0.769	
▪ Calculated F		327.879	
▪ Degree of Freedom		3, 296	
▪ Indexed F		3.78	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01			

As Table (11) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.877 demonstrates that the independent variables of OI construe OS significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, independent variables of OI can explain 77% of the total factors in OS level. Hence, 23% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

7.6. OI as a Mediating Variable of the Relationship between SL and OS

The statistically significant effect of OI as a mediating variable of the relationship between SL and OS is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

H4: There is no significant effect of OI as a mediating variable of the relationship between SL and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate."

The study of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable through the intermediate variable is an important subject in social studies. The researcher relied on Holmbeck (1997) to measure the role of OI as an intermediate variable in interpreting the impact of SL on OS by testing three different models. This can be illustrated as follows:

7.6.1. Full Direct Effects Model

This model is based on the fact that the independent variable (SL) directly affects the dependent variable (OS) in addition to the direct relationship between the mediating variable (OI) and the dependent variable (OS). The structural model of the direct and complete effect of the search variables can be illustrated by the following diagram:

Figure (2)
The structural model of the direct and complete effect of the search variables

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the previous figure, there is a direct effect of the independent variable (SL) on the dependent variable (OS), and the direct effect of the variable (OI) on the dependent variable (OS). The correlation quality indicators of the direct and complete impact model can be illustrated in the following table:

Table (12)
Match quality indicators for the direct impact model of search variables

Test the Quality of the Model	Test Value	Acceptance Condition ^(*)
X ² / Degree of freedom	2015.416	(X ² / df) < 5
P. value	0.000	P > 0.5
Goodness of fit Index (GFI)	0.733	GFI > 0.90
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI)	0.547	TLI > 0.9
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.698	CFI > 0.95
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.694	NFI > 0.90
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.699	IFI > 0.9

(*) Daire et al., 2008

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the above-mentioned indicators, it is clear that the model has achieved good indicators according to the results of the analysis, where the value of ($\chi^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$) 2015.416 is greater than (5), and the value of P is significant. The index of the Goodness of fit Index (GFI = 0,733) is less than (0.9) in addition to the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.547) which is less than (0.9), as well as the value of the Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.698), less than (0.9), the Normed Fit Index (NFI = 0.694), less than 0.9, and Incremental Fit Index (IFI = 0.699), which is less than 0.9.

Accordingly, it should be noted that all the previous indicators confirm that all model estimates are significant, indicating that there is a relationship between SL and OS, on the one hand, OI, and OS on the other.

According to the above-mentioned results, it was decided to reject the null hypothesis that said: "there is no significant influence on both SL and OI on OS." The alternative hypothesis was accepted after it was found that the independent variable (SL) had an effect on the dependent variable (OS) on the one hand, and the direct effect of OI on the OS (dependent variable) on the other. This decision was based on the value of ($\chi^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$), the value of (P), and the indicators of GFI, TLI, CFI, NFI, IFI.

7.6.2. Full Mediated Model

This model is based on the fact that OI mediates the relationship between SL and OS. The structural model of the full mediation of the search variables can be illustrated in the following form:

Figure (3)

A structural model for full mediation of search variables

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the previous figure, it is clear that there is a direct influence of the independent variable (SL) on the dependent variable (OS). The correlation quality indicators for this model can be illustrated by Table (32), which shows that the model achieved good indicators according to the results of the analysis, where the value ($\chi^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$) 1925.310 is greater than (5), and that the value of P is significant. The index of the Goodness of fit Index (GFI = 0.665) is less than (0.9) in addition to the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.365), which is less than (0.9), as well as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.633), less than (0.9), the Normed Fit Index (NFI = 0.631), less than 0.9, and the Incremental Fit Index (IFI = 0.635), which is less than 0.9. Accordingly, it should be noted that all previous indicators confirm that all estimates of the model are significant, which shows that there is a relationship between SL and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.

According to the above-mentioned results, it was decided to reject the null hypothesis that said: "there is no effect of SL, on OS." The alternative hypothesis was accepted after it was found that the independent variable (SL) had an impact on the dependent variable (OS). This decision was based on the value of ($\chi^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$), the value of (P), and the indicators of GFI, TLI, CFI, NFI, IFI.

Table (13)

Match quality indicators for the direct impact model of search variables

Test the Quality of the Model	Test Value	Acceptance Condition (*)
X ² / Degree of freedom	1925.310	(X ² /df) < 5
P. value	0.000	P> 0.5
Goodness of fit Index (GFI)	0.665	GFI > 0.90
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI)	0.365	TLI > 0.9
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.633	CFI > 0.95
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.631	NFI > 0.90
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.635	IFI > 0.9

(*) Daire et al., 2008

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

7.6.3. Partial Mediated Model

This model is based on the indirect effect of the independent variable (SL) and the dependent variable (OS) through the intermediate variable (OI).

Figure (4)

The structural model of the search variables

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

It is clear that there is an indirect influence between the SL (the independent variable) on OS (the dependent variable) through OI (the mediating variable). The different indicators of the quality of the partial mediation model can be explained in the following table:

Table (14)

Match quality indicators for the direct impact model of search variables

Test the Quality of the Model	Test Value	Acceptance Condition (*)
X ² / Degree of freedom	1817.940	(X ² /df) < 5
P. value	0.000	P> 0.5
Goodness of fit Index (GFI)	0.764	GFI > 0.90
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI)	0.584	TLI > 0.9
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.728	CFI > 0.95
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.724	NFI > 0.90
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.335	IFI > 0.9

(*) Daire et al., 2008

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the above-mentioned indicators, it is clear that the model achieved good indicators according to the results of the analysis, where the value of ($\chi^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$) 1817.940 is greater than (5), and the value of P is significant. The index of the Goodness of fit Index (GFI = 0.764) is less than (0.9) in addition to the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.584), which is less than (0.9), as well as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.728), less than (0.9), the Normed Fit Index (NFI = 0.724), less than 0.9, and the Incremental Fit Index (IFI = 0.335), which is less than 0.9.

Accordingly, it should be noted that all the previous indicators confirm that all model estimates are significant, which shows that there is an indirect relationship between SL and OS through OI; that is, OI plays the role of partial mediation between SL and OS in Menoufia University Hospitals.

In the light of the above, the Sobel test was carried out in order to measure the indirect effects of SL (independent variable) on OS (dependent variable) through OI (mediating variable). Therefore, the previous results are not significant unless after testing Sobel.

The Sobel test depends on the value of the Z value. If the Z value is greater than 1.96, we conclude that the model is an intermediate variable model; that is, the indirect effect is true and vice versa if the Z value is less than 1.96. This can be illustrated by Table (34), which shows that there is a significant indirect effect of OI (mediator variable) on the relationship between SL (independent variable) and OS (dependent variable).

Table (15)
Sobel Test

Significance Indirect Effect	Test Value
Effect Degree	0.6729
Standard Error	0.0551
The Value of Calculated Z	12.220
Degree of Freedom	2, 297
The Value of Indexed Z	1.96
P. value	0.000

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the previous table, there is a significant effect of OI (mediating variable) on the relationship between SL (independent variable) and OS (dependent variable).

According to the above-mentioned results, it was decided to reject the null hypothesis that said: "there is no significant effect of OI as a mediating variable of the relationship between SL and OS at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate." The alternative hypothesis was accepted after it was found that there is a significant effect of SL (independent variable) on the OS (dependent variable through the mediating variable (OI), that is, OI plays the mediating role on the relationship between SL and OS. This decision was based on the value of the $\chi^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$, the value of P, the GFI, TLI, CFI, NFI, IFI and Sobel tests.

8. Research Findings

By reviewing the results of the descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the hypotheses of the research, the study reached a set of results as follows:

1. The existence of a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of SL (vision, hope/faith, love of altruism, the meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, productivity) and the dimensions of OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, and membership) at commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Erkutlu et al., 2016, in which he concluded that there is a relationship between the integrity of the leader's behavior and the OI; that is, the behavioral integrity of the leader enhances the OI of the employees. Therefore, leaders must take into account their actions and behavior within the organization in a way that increases the process of identification among them.

2. There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of SL (vision, hope/faith, altruism, the meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, productivity) and OS (organizational survival and organizational growth). The multiple regression model showed that the dimensions of SL as an independent variable affect OS as a variable in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia governorate. This finding is consistent with Fry's 2003 study, in which Glee points out that SL plays an important role in OS in a highly uncertain environment.
3. There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of OI (organizational loyalty, organizational similarity, membership) and OS (organizational survival and organizational growth) after the multiple regression model showed that the dimensions of SL have an independent variable on OS as a dependent variable in Commercial Public Sector Banks in Menoufia Governorate.
4. There is a direct influence of the independent variable (SL) on the dependent variable (OS) on the one hand and the direct effect of the variable (OI) on the dependent variable (OS) on the other. In other words, there is a partial effect of the organizational variable on the relationship between the independent variable (SL) and the dependent variable (OS); that is, OI plays a partial role in the relationship between SL and OS in public sector commercial banks Governorate of Menoufia.
5. There is a direct effect of the independent variable (SL) on the dependent variable (OS). In other words, OI mediates the relationship between SL and OS in public sector commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate.
6. There is an indirect influence between SL and OS through OI as an intermediate variable. In other words, there is an indirect influence of the independent variable (SL) on the dependent variable (OS) through the medium variable (OI). In other words, OI plays the role of partial mediation in the relationship between SL and OS in public sector commercial banks in the governorate of Menoufia.

9. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations. The most important of these recommendations can be summarized as follows:

1. The need for managers in the commercial public sector banks in Menoufia governorate to be aware of the future vision. This can be done through the involvement of the employees in their situation, which entails exerting the effort and striving towards achieving them.
2. The managers of the commercial public sector banks in Menoufia governorate should have hope and faith in the vision of the bank. This can be done through financial rewards, on the one hand, and involvement in their development, on the other.
3. The need to have a love of altruism among leaders in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia, by teaching the values of patience, honesty, anger, sense of failure, false pride.
4. The necessity of conviction of all employees in the public sector commercial banks in the governorate of Menoufia; that is, the jobs they do have significance and meaning both for them and others.
5. The need to deepen the membership in the public sector commercial banks in the governorate of Menoufia with all employees, as the sense of employees belonging to the bank, creates an atmosphere of friendliness and trust among employees, employees and their leaders.
6. The need for managers in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia to raise the level of organizational commitment. This can be done by improving the leadership methods that lead to increased employee satisfaction of employees. This raises the level of their organizational commitment.
7. The need for managers in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia governorate to increase productivity and continuous improvement, as the availability of hope and faith in the vision of the organization and their sense of importance and members will do their best to achieve the vision and mission of the Organization and to try to improve continuously.
8. The managers in the commercial public sector banks in Menoufia should have the basic qualifications of the leadership, which includes vision, faith, and hope, as well as the need to create an atmosphere of spirituality in the workplace to reach a more efficient and effective environment.
9. Officials in the public sector commercial banks in the governorate of Menoufia should pay attention to employees, through the identification of their wishes and needs realizing them commensurate with their objectives in order to improve the process of OI.

10. The need to invest in learning in the promotion and development of OS opportunities. This can be done by encouraging the senior management of the learning process itself, open channels of communication, promoting teamwork, and enabling the staff to perform the tasks assigned to them.
11. Designing and implementing a series of specialized training programs for all officials in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate. This can be accomplished by raising awareness among the administrative leaders about the concept, importance, areas of OI, and its positive effects: hard-working employees, increased affiliation and loyalty to the bank, increase in the degree of commitment to work, increase the degree of cohesion, cooperation, participation, coordination, ease of communication between them, the degree of commitment to the values and objectives of the bank, and achievement of its objectives for the benefit of the bank. The desire of membership in it, continuous service, workflow, low turnover, increased level of job satisfaction, deepening organizational citizenship behavior will improve job performance.
12. Increasing the interest of the employees in the commercial public sector banks in Menoufia governorate and identifying their needs and desires periodically to achieve and satisfy the possible ones. The administrative leaders should clarify the objectives that the bank seeks to achieve and work to involve the employees in identifying and setting them.
13. Officials in the public sector commercial banks in the governorate of Menoufia increase the level of OI of employees. This can be achieved by inviting employees to participate in decision-making by providing their views and suggestions. Participation in decision-making gives it the status of realism and creates their motivation to implement the decision seriously because of their sense that the decision is theirs at the bank level.
14. To direct the attention of officials in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia governorate to strengthen the OI among employees, through continuous meetings, social and recreational activities, for greater cohesion, interdependence, and effectiveness among employees.
15. To direct the attention of officials in the public sector commercial banks in Menoufia Governorate towards maintaining the level of OI. This can be done through the creation of working conditions, the use of the incentives method, whether physical or moral, and the design of performance-related incentive systems, since incentives play an important role in maintaining the level of OI, on the one hand, and positively influence the level of functionality, on the other

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